

The Small Business Ideas are Origin for Great Business Innovations

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Abstract

In the 21st Century the buzzword is often used in all fields is “Innovation”. We can see many start-up companies, which are either product development or Service oriented, which are small scale or big scale. The owners of these companies belong to various age groups but their business model would be giving solution to our current problems or perennial Problems of Society. The new ideas of their business models are mostly basic solution of the current problem. If you look in to their business in depth, we can realize that they are solution provider of our everlasting difficulties. In this paper, presentation would like to deal with the ideas are how important and how these ideas are tweaked in to business for current scenario and how small business with low investment helps to reap maximum benefits. This presentation explains how existing ideas can be modified in to new ideas according to the context and requirement of the consumer. Various ways of generating ideas and how those ideas are basis for great innovations. This paper also discusses about various low investment small businesses existing in India and there is an analysis on how these businesses help societal problem in day-to-day life. Apart from that, it narrates how our Indian constitution helps to promote start-ups, small business, and Woman entrepreneurship in coming years.

Keywords: Information Technology: Innovation, Idea generation, tools & techniques.

Introduction

From the inception of globalization, many start-up companies are innumerable in count started by youngsters who are all having many new ideas to address social problems. All young students interest has been invoked during their school days itself. There are many competitions are being conducted among students for creativity and implementation of their creative ideas through lot of technology exhibitions. Therefore, while they are coming up with their graduation, their mind is full of enthusiasm of starting their own business with novel ideas. The friends and network nurture their ideas from the seed form. The result is those matured ideas become their dream and like to start their own business in a small scale. Since our Indian culture changed in the way that the mind set of young generation also changed. In the past few decades, youngsters were interested in investing their money in buying houses and buying new cars. Instead, they want to start new companies and would like to become entrepreneurs. The reasons for their entrepreneurship is would like to give employment to few of his known people as well as not having interest in working

under somebody. There are many ways for starting small-scale business. But nowadays most of our startup companies with low investments is solution to our social problems .From food to digital games there are umpteen number of startup companies with small scale investment which are foundation of big business.

Nation level Interest on Small-scale start-ups

India improved its ranking in the Global Innovation Index (GII) by five places to 52nd in 2019 from 57th position last year, according to a report released by our Commerce and Industry Minister Piyush Goyal.Mr. Modi become our Prime minister successfully second time to our country. His government moves to embrace a growth model that follows Japan, South Korea and China in innovation and economic growth. India has been flaunted to become third-largest economy of the world by 2030 because India possesses democracy, demography as well as largest population of youth. Our country is very keen in developing skills of youth. The finance minister Nirmala Seetharaman, proposed a scheme during Budget 2019, on fostering talent, entrepreneurship and skill updation to youth. She has announced about the starting an exclusive TV channel for start-ups.

The success of India’s startups has infused new life into its economy, workplaces, and the general entrepreneurial spirit among Indians. These startups have been crucial in solving many societal and business problems, including job creation. The government’s laser focus on startups in the Budget is a step towards nurturing an enabling ecosystem for startups. The expectation is to boost the entrepreneurial spirit and spur innovative ideas, especially pertaining to the agro-rural sector that has been facing greater stress.

The focus on empowering women, especially in rural areas, is commendable. India has taken special steps to create enablement of women and special loans for women entrepreneurs to start small-scale business with low investment. The loan bearers would repay their loans in monthly installment basis as per the profit of the business. The appropriate trainings will be given to them to start their own business to be self-reliant.

Small scale Business

When we start to think about small business there are many fields and diversified businesses. They crop up in the world in abundance. We cannot point out only specified area of development of small business .There are many businesses in different area that we never think before. The pick of that small-scale business is proportional to the need of consumers.New ideas are implemented for creation of startup business in various portfolios. I remember one of the quote on Startup is “If you want to build a Start-up, you find a problem first”. The best part about problems is that they are everywhere and every area, locality, city, country, demographics have their own problems. If you are able to spot, the problem you want to solve it will give your idea as solution to the problem.

Health: Nowadays people are having awareness on their health and very keen on their fitness by doing exercises and yoga. Starting yoga sessions is a lucrative method, as not everyone does correctly. So you can become an yoga trainer .Recently in our corporate to create health awareness to employees, organization arranged ZUMBA session in which everyone involved in dancing in the way of exercises to famous cine songs . It was very funny and useful. Anybody who is having vast knowledge on exercise equipment, start a shop by keeping all exercises tools. In most of the organizations/Schools/ Colleges to propaganda health awareness or any of the noble cause to the society Marathon(Running race). Few event management group organizes suchMarathons, which is a profitable business.

Food: If you are really having talent in cooking and great experimenter of new recipes, the organizing cooking classes is a great time pass and profitable business for women.

In the meantime, the cook should be good at sales and marketing. These skills will help to expand their cooking business. It is Internet world. You can upload your cooking video in You Tube and lot of people subscribe your video, the cook would get lump sum of money from the host. In the current generation lot of girls are not able to cook properly because of their employment or any other outside responsibilities. In ant festival or occasions, they are in need of good cook to scale up their cooking. All cook charge nearly 4000 to 500 per day for cooking 10 people. If you develop, your cooking skill along with conserving ingredients is an added advantage. Delivering food at their food steps becomes great business. We are all aware of Uber Eats, Swiggy and Zomato. Everyone is now concerned about what they eat and when they should eat it. If you have a good knowledge about food and its nutrients, you could start giving advice to people and giving them health tips as well. This is sure to bring in some cash for you.

Wow! Momo, is one of the biggest start-up in India. This is Kolkata based Startup Company which has fast-food chains in India. It has verity of Momos maze of Corn Cheese, Burgers and verity of delicious Momos. This Startup Company started its branches in all main cities such as Bangalore, Chennai, Pune, Delhi, Kochi & Noida.

Food Products

Ice creams are very longer a seasonal treat and most of the people prefer different flavours as per their taste. Learning new flavors, of ice creams and selling to different customers according to their taste is small-scale industry.

Famous Achi Masala & Sakthi Masala centers appointed many disabled women for their Cooking powder's preparation. Chocolate is a treat that almost everyone loves. Even most of the homemakers during their free time, they used to start small business such as variety of homemade chocolates and Cakes preparations. This business brings a lump sum of money and their leisure time is spent in useful ways. Pappats, Jams, Chips and fries are made available because of many start-up companies employed women who are abandoned by their close relatives. Starting Bakery shop is an ideal one for fastest profits.

Grocery Delivery Business: There are many such online booking and home delivery things are happening. Amazon & Big basket are very famous online shopping and prices with discounted rate. Most of the people are too busy, they do not find time for going to shops in their day-to-day life, Since Internet is persuasive, and booking in online is easiest job. So grocery delivery business becomes lucrative now.

One of the interesting blog, I read recently which gives short cut like Amazon book centers suggested the following tips. The business model is just Develop a grocery website. Unlike the other grocery sites, collect orders from the customers and deliver it only on first weekend of every month to meet their monthly requirements. This model has This model we will have following advantages such as no Inventory cost (by taking orders for entire month and purchase in bulk and deliver it to customers, No rental cost for storing items and less man hours.

Catering Services: Not only women but also all educated youth start catering services which is common business and easy way of earning money double their investment. There is larger demands during marriage seasons and all sort of community people prefers arranging catering services for their domestic function. It is actually win-win situation for ordering party as well as catering service personnel. The famous marriage catering services are Arusuvai, Natarajan, and Gnanambika & Vinayaka Catering.

Events

The great event such as wedding, the Wedding planner start-up is the best suggestions to go far. In this hurry burry world, people do not find time to organize all things on a particular day. The wedding planner from the day start of wedding to until end of the function, entire arrangements are taken care of by them.

Nowadays Corporates are also behind event management companies to render their services for Summit, Annual day, Family day & Employees recognition day. Inspiring employees for participation is also their responsibility. During their event, mostly all employees are involved by them and make a memorable event for all employees by engaging them.

Transport

Recently I have seen in the newspaper that automobile industry is down and the sales of cars becomes down. If you look in to the reason, recent past the mindset of youngsters has been changed. They do not want to be an owner of cars instead prefer to commute by Ola & Uber. By using technology, if you book an Ola or Uber, the next five minutes will get a car for your use, there is another new concept is Taxi – application for Independent drivers. Drivers or Car owners can fix the rate; it will be helpful for them and fixed neither rates nor minimum rides per day. In the perspective of user, they may get lower fares than the other taxi apps. They get taxi during peak hours without indirect charges. There are many Car Driving schools in many areas where majority of the people do not know to drive. There is another lucrative business is Used Car dealership through which many contacts can be developed.

Saree & Boutique

The modern girls prefer of clothing business opportunity that would always ensure reasonable profits. If they really do the business with so much dedication, it brings lot of customers through existing customers. In major metro cities, fashion cloths are sold in boutiques. The modern girls like to wear modern dresses and not bothering about its prices. There is another way of doing is Garment Distribution. In this business, no need to set-up a shop. Selling garments on credit basis to shops as well as individual customers. The pain in this business is following-up them continuously for getting payments

Conclusion

For any start-up companies, ideas are fundamental. Getting ideas is easy from human beings. However, execution of ideas is challenging one. I remember one quote from Sue Grafton that “Ideas are easy. It’s the execution of ideas that really separates the sheep from the goats”. Therefore, the most important part is execution, which requires time and endurance. There is a perception that all innovations are only technology innovation. However, it is not true, because above narrated all start-up companies are solution providers to society problems or addressing common person’s basic requirements. Apart from using Government benefits for starting small-scale business, but also advertising their business by using technological media is essential. The entrepreneurs should know to market their business by social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, writing Blogs and creating their own website. It is sometimes hard for small businesses, who have a lower budget to carry out market research; blog would be great medium for their business. Even small start-up, an Entrepreneurship is not as smooth as butter. It takes passion, dedication, hard work, brilliance, skills and most important thing, entrepreneur loves his business more than anything does.

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